

Natural ways of mapping subsets to subsets

Pierre-Yves Gaillard

If X is a set, M its monoid of self-maps and P its power set, then P can be viewed as a left M -set ${}_M P$ or as a right M -set P_M . We compute the monoids $\text{End } {}_M P$ and $\text{End } P_M$.

Let X be a set, $M = X^X$ its monoid of self-maps (that is, $M = \{f : X \rightarrow X\}$) and P its power set (that is, $P = \{A \mid A \subset X\}$). Then P has a left M -set structure given by

$$fA = f_*A = \{fa \mid a \in A\}$$

and a right M -set structure given by

$$Af = f^*A = f^{-1}A = \{x \in X \mid fx \in A\}.$$

We denote these two M -sets by ${}_M P$ and P_M respectively. Our purpose is to compute the monoids $\text{End } {}_M P$ and $\text{End } P_M$. In the sequel we denote fA and Af by f_*A and f^*A respectively.

Define the maps $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta : P \rightarrow P$ by the formulas

$$\alpha A = A, \quad \beta A = \emptyset, \quad \gamma A = X \setminus A, \quad \delta A = A.$$

(Here \emptyset is the empty set and $X \setminus A$ the complement of A in X .)

Theorem 1. *We have $\text{End } {}_M P = \{\alpha, \beta\}$ and $\text{End } P_M = \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta\}$.*

It suffices to show $\text{End } {}_M P \subset \{\alpha, \beta\}$ and $\text{End } P_M \subset \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta\}$. Indeed, the converse inclusions are clear. Moreover, to prove Theorem 1 we can, and do, assume that X has at least two elements.

1 The monoid $\text{End } {}_M P$

The M -sets considered in this section are **left** M -sets.

Lemma 2. *If $\varepsilon : P \rightarrow P$ is a morphism of M -sets, then $\varepsilon \in \{\alpha, \beta\}$.*

Proof. This will follow immediately from the four steps below.

Step 1: We have $\varepsilon \emptyset = \emptyset$. Proof: The equalities $\varepsilon \emptyset = \varepsilon f_* \emptyset = f_* \varepsilon \emptyset$ hold for all f in M . This implies $\varepsilon \emptyset = \emptyset$.

Note: In view of Step 1 it suffices to show that we have either $\varepsilon A = \emptyset$ for all A in P , $A \neq \emptyset$, or $\varepsilon A = A$ for all A in P , $A \neq \emptyset$.

Step 2: We have $\varepsilon X \in \{\emptyset, X\}$. Proof: Since $\varepsilon f_* X = f_* \varepsilon X$ for all f in M , we get $\varepsilon X = f_* \varepsilon X$ for all surjection $f : X \rightarrow X$, and thus $\varepsilon X \in \{\emptyset, X\}$.

Step 3: If $\varepsilon X = \emptyset$, then $\varepsilon = \beta$. Proof: We have $\varepsilon f_* X = f_* \emptyset = \emptyset$ for all f in M . This entails $\varepsilon A = \emptyset$ for all A in P , $A \neq \emptyset$, hence $\varepsilon = \beta$ by the Note.

Step 4: If $\varepsilon X = X$, then $\varepsilon = \alpha$. Proof: We have $\varepsilon f_* X = f_* X$ for all f in M . This implies $\varepsilon A = A$ for all A in P , $A \neq \emptyset$, hence $\varepsilon = \alpha$ by the Note. \square

2 The monoid $\text{End } P_M$

The M -sets considered in this section are **right** M -sets.

Let $\varepsilon : P \rightarrow P$ be a morphism of M -sets. We must show:

Lemma 3. *If $\varepsilon : P \rightarrow P$ is a morphism of M -sets, then $\varepsilon \in \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta\}$.*

Proof. We generalize slightly the notation used so far. Set $2 := \{0, 1\}$. For all set Y write Y^* for the set of subsets of Y and identify Y^* to the set 2^Y of all maps $Y \rightarrow 2$ by attaching to $A \subset Y$ the map f defined by $fx = 1$ if and only if $x \in A$. Moreover we associate with a map $g : Z \rightarrow Y$ the map $g^* : Y^* \rightarrow Z^*$ defined by $g^*A = g^{-1}(A)$. Note that, if $f : Y \rightarrow 2$ is the map attached to A described above, then the map $Z \rightarrow 2$ attached to g^*A is $f \circ g$, so that it is natural to denote this map by g^*f .

Claim: If A is a nonempty proper subset of X , then $\varepsilon A \in \{\emptyset, A, X \setminus A, X\}$.

Proof of the claim. Let A be as above and $f : X \rightarrow 2$ the map attached to A . Since for any $B \subset 2$ we have $f^*B \in \{\emptyset, A, X \setminus A, X\}$, it suffices to show that εA is of the form f^*B with $B \subset 2$. Pick x_0 in $X \setminus A$ and x_1 in A , and define $g : 2 \rightarrow X$ by $g(i) = x_i$. Then $f \circ g$ is the identity of 2 , and we get

$$\varepsilon A = \varepsilon f = \varepsilon(f \circ g \circ f) = \varepsilon((g \circ f)^*(f)) = (g \circ f)^*(\varepsilon f) = f^*(g^* \varepsilon f).$$

This proves the claim.

Recall that A is a nonempty proper subset of X . Let C be any subset of X , define $h \in M$ by $hx = x_1$ if $x \in C$ and $hx = x_0$ if $x \in X \setminus C$, and observe the equalities $h^*A = C$ and $\varepsilon C = \varepsilon h^*A = h^* \varepsilon A$. The claim implies $\varepsilon A \in \{\emptyset, A, X \setminus A, X\}$. If $\varepsilon A = \emptyset$ then $\varepsilon C = h^* \emptyset = \emptyset$. If $\varepsilon A = A$ then $\varepsilon C = h^*A = C$. The cases $\varepsilon A = X \setminus A$ and $\varepsilon A = X$ are similar. This shows $\varepsilon \in \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta\}$, as desired. \square

Now Theorem 1 follows from Lemmas 2 and 3.